

Research Article

EduTag: A Low-Cost IoT-based Smart Attendance System for Higher Education Environments

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Abstract: In an environment where a large scale of crowd gathers such as university mass lectures with over 50 attendees where attendance is compulsory, recording and managing attendance accurately and efficiently becomes a challenging yet essential task for the instructors and administrative staff. The traditional attendance systems require attendees to manually sign in for the attendance records that are prone to human error such as illegible handwriting, missing signatures, or incorrect dates. Furthermore, this method is vulnerable to attendance falsification through buddy punching. Some institutions might resort to thumb print recognition system to capture the attendance, but this method is time consuming as the finger must be at the correct position and precisely aligned with the scanner so that the system can match it with the stored image, which often results in delays and bottlenecks. Quick Response (QR) code is another popular method for attendance taking, which required the use smartphones. However, this method may lead to falsification of attendance as well, as QR codes can easily be shared with other students who might not even be in the classroom, compromising the integrity of attendance data. Therefore, to mitigate these problems, we are proposing the use of RFID cards that have read/write capability. As a proof of concept, a prototype model was built using an ESP32 microcontroller, a pair of RFID reader and card, and an LCD screen. When students attend the class, they will tap their RFID card against the reader, the system will instantly record and store the student's name, student ID, and timestamps in a cloud storage. The LCD screen will also display student's name, student ID, and timestamps. Since all the data are stored digitally, this solution reduces the administrative workload and ensures accuracy of the data stored. Additionally, it not only enhances efficiency and transparency but also supports environmental sustainability by reducing paper usage. We have tested this prototype, and it seems to be working well. This is a simple solution and cheap implementation for a class attendance system. In the future, we plan to substitute RFID cards with actual student's card in the prototype and explore the potential of using GPS to track student actual location in the system.

Keywords: attendance system; IoT; ESP32; microcontroller.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's higher educational environment, maintaining accurate and efficient attendance records has become an essential part of academic management. Usually, paper-based forms are used when taking attendance, where they are being passed around the classroom to get students' signature. However, managing attendance of mass lectures in big classrooms remains a persistent challenge due to the inefficiency of the manual attendance system.

While keeping track of students in a class is a time-consuming activity in any institution, class attendance remains a powerful predictor of student success. Numerous studies have shown that students who attend classes regularly perform better academically and are more likely to complete their studies (Heather, 2025). Awareness of attendance tracking also increases motivation and engagement among students, improving completion rates and overall learning outcomes. Despite its obvious drawbacks, many institutions still relying on the traditional attendance taking method. Other problems or issues with using manual attendance taking in higher education includes human error, such as illegible handwriting, missing signatures, or incorrect dates, and buddy punching, where students signing in on behalf of their friends, which lead to inaccurate records.

Consequently, with the increase use of smartphones, Quick Response (QR) code has become popular method for attendance taking (Jadhav et al, 2023). However, this method may lead to falsification of attendance as well, as QR codes can easily be shared with other students who might not even be in the classroom. Moreover, the integration of advanced technologies like face recognition, IoT, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), and cloud computing is able to automate and improve accuracy, accountability, and efficiency in attendance tracking across educational environments. Even so, there are still flaws found in certain alternatives. For instance, biometric devices such as face and thumb print recognitions are prone to issues like sensor failure, wear-and-tear, or environmental sensitivity — dirty fingers, extreme temperatures, or humidity can cause frequent reading errors and inaccurate attendance logs. Biometric attendance system is also lacking in conveniency — single terminals might lead to long queues and frustration during attendance marking (HRMex, 2024).

To address these challenges, this project proposes an IoT-based smart attendance system utilising RFID technology, ESP32 microcontroller, and cloud storage for real-time data management. In this system, each student is provided an RFID card — each contains a unique identification code. When the card is tapped on the RFID reader, the ESP32 processes the data and transmits it to a cloud server via Wi-Fi for real-time storage. The system also includes an LCD display that shows the student's name, ID, and timestamp upon successful attendance marking. By integrating IoT and cloud computing, this system ensures fast, accurate, and reliable attendance tracking. Furthermore, the use of digital data storage promotes transparency, security, and environmental sustainability by eliminating the need of paper-based attendance sheets.

The main goal for this project is to provide a cheaper, efficient, and sustainable solution in managing class attendance in higher education environments, especially for university mass lectures.

2. METHODOLOGY

EduTag Smart Attendance System was developed with the implementation of Internet of Things (IoT) to replace manual processes with an interconnected flow of data. As a proof of concept, we have built a prototype comprises of components as listed in Figure 1, and the schematic design of the prototype is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Hardware Components

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram

The system was programmed using Arduino IDE to control the ESP32 and manage RFID data reading. The ESP32 was connected to Wi-Fi to enable cloud data transmission. The system utilised Google Sheet as the cloud database because of its accessibility and easy integration with Google Apps Script. A custom Google Apps Script was written to act as a web API endpoint. When a student tapped their RFID card on the reader, the ESP32 send the student’s ID, name, and timestamp to the web script through an HTTP POST request. The script the automatically appended the received data into the designated Google Sheet, creating an instant digital attendance record. This setup provided a real-time, secure, and paperless storage solution that could be accessed and monitored by lecturers or administrators.

The prototype was tested to evaluate its speed, accuracy, and reliability. An RFID card was registered and used to simulate student attendance in a session. The card was scanned several times to measure detection speed and record attendance within one second of tapping, and the entries were accurately stored in the Google Sheet without duplication or data loss. The system performed optimally under stable Wi-Fi conditions and demonstrated excellent consistency in reading RFID cards and updating cloud data. There are two modes — ‘Registration’ and ‘Attendance’. During ‘Registration’ mode, an RFID card is tapped against the reader for the first time to be marked as new user, as shown in Figure 3. After the data is fully keyed in, the mode can be changed into ‘Attendance’ and immediately record the users’ record, as shown in Figure 4.

	A	B	C	D
1	Name	UID		
2	BRYAN	2F341EFC		
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				

Figure 3. Registration Mode on Google Sheet

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Name	UID	Date	Time In	Time Out			
2	MASON	2F341EFC	29/10/2025	12:13:45	12:14:07			
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								
12								
13								
14								
15								
16								
17								

Figure 4. Attendance Mode on Google Sheet

3. FINDINGS

The prototype system was tested with an RFID card by re-entering both ‘Registration’ and ‘Attendance’ mode to test its response speed and accuracy. Testing activities are shown in Figure 5, Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8. Results showed that all cards were successfully detected within an average response time of 0.8 seconds. The LCD display correctly showed the student’s name, and timestamp after each scan, and the data was immediately transmitted and stored in the cloud database. No duplicate entries or false reading were recorded, confirming the reliability and accuracy of the prototype.

Figure 5. The Prototype

Figure 6. 'Registration' Mode

Figure 7. 'Attendance' Mode

Figure 8. Attendance Successfully Recorded

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the testing performed, EduTag offers a reliable and efficient alternative to traditional attendance methods. Compared to manual sign-ins or biometric systems, the proposed system solution significantly reduces the time needed to record the attendance while maintaining high accuracy. The automatic transmission of data to a cloud server also eliminates the risk of data loss and potential fraud while ensuring a secure digital storage. RFID-based attendance system is proven to be reducing manual errors and improve efficiency (Ali et al., 2022). However, the system's performance depends on stable Internet connectivity and the proximity of the RFID card to the reader. Future recommendations may include integrating the system with existing student ID cards and developing a mobile-based interface to enhance accessibility and flexibility. Overall, the results demonstrate the system's potential to streamline attendance management and support the digital transformation of educational environments.

5. CONCLUSION

EduTag was designed to provide a smart, low-cost, and reliable attendance tracking system compared to the traditional method. This system really helps especially in mass lectures as it saves a lot of time and minimises errors such as proxy attendance and students forgetting to sign. The prototype achieved its objective by automating the attendance process and eliminating the inefficiencies of traditional methods. This project provides a simple yet scalable solution that can be adopted in educational environments to enhance productivity and data accuracy. In the future, the system can be improved by combining the functions of students' matrix card and the RFID identification card in one integrated system and adding additional features such as mobile-based or GPS apps to increase the efficiency of the system.

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